

Project Report on LC Circuit Analog of an Electromagnetically Induced Transparent System

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What happens when there is an ordinary wall and we switch on a light against it? The natural answer is the light ray gets absorbed and one cannot see the light standing on opposite side of the wall. What if we have a special kind of wall, and some special sources of light, such that shooting one such light beam against the wall, and then another light beam followed by it, makes a way for the first light beam to go past the wall?! Wont it be great? In fact, the case is if that imaginary wall is an atomic energy level and the two special sources of light are two Coupled Lasers, then this is what happens in reality!

The phenomenon of such induced transparency of a light beam is called Electromagnetically Induced Transparency (EIT). What happens can be shown by the diagram below:

Fig (1)

The Fig (1) shows the EIT phenomenon using an atomic model of three increasing energy levels $|1\rangle$, $|2\rangle$ & $|3\rangle$. What happening here is that a laser called “pump” laser, of frequency ω_c , which is used to make transition of ground energy level $|3\rangle$ to excited energy level $|2\rangle$. In accordance with the Principle of Superposition in Quantum Mechanics, there is an infinite number of paths the energy level transitions can take place & addition of probabilities of all of the possible paths gives us our most probable path from $|3\rangle$ to $|2\rangle$. The addition of probabilities of all the paths means adding the individual phases of the paths which will leave us with two paths which is least probable, arising due to destructive interference of the paths and one most probable which arises due to constructive interference of the paths. Therefore, due to the laser field at $|3\rangle$ and its transition to energy level $|2\rangle$, $|2\rangle$ splits into two different energy levels due to two independent paths resultant from the interference, which is also known as the Stark Effect. Now if another laser beam called the “probe” laser, of frequency ω_p is turned on and it makes transition from another ground state $|1\rangle$, it will pass between two split energy levels, resultant from path interference of transition of “pump” laser from $|3\rangle$ to $|2\rangle$ without getting absorbed into $|2\rangle$. Therefore, the “pump” laser makes a “tunnel” for “probe” laser to move through the medium by interfering with the energy level and changing the absorption property of the medium. In other it makes the medium transparent for the “probe” laser to pass through it.

The entire phenomenon has been observed in the laboratory and researchers worldwide have put forth models to perform much elaborate experiments to achieve some wonderful effects caused by the phenomenon such as alteration of group velocity of a light, and slowing it down or even stopping it, which is known as the “Slow Light”. The phenomenon can also be modelled and observed using simple Coupled Oscillator Circuit consisting a Capacitors & Inductors. The currents in the Coupled Oscillator Circuit acts as the “probe” and the “pump” lasers, the energy levels of atom is analogically be the potential at the central capacitor Q_3 .

Fig (2): Coupled A.C. Oscillator Circuits have multiple oscillating current direction, which interferes and gives two output resultant voltages, maximum & minimum, and a voltage drop in between.

Fig(3): Non-Coupled A.C. Oscillator Circuit which has a single direction of current does not show any interference and hence there will be no voltage drop.

The current in a Coupled Oscillator Circuit splits into two directions at the junction and the two currents interfere in the junction again after a time cycle to produce a resultant current and therefore a resultant voltage at the junction capacitor Q_3 is obtained with a voltage drop when the frequency of the current becomes equal to the driving A.C. Voltage V_s as the following equations proves.

The equations for Coupled Oscillator will be as follows, if current $I_1 = x_1$ & $I_2 = x_2$ & electrical resistance for I_1 & I_2 being γ_1 & γ_2 angular frequency of the current being ω , that of A.C. Voltage being ω_s , & Couple frequency being Ω_c , also applied voltage being E_0 ,

$$\ddot{x}_1 + \gamma_1 \dot{x}_1 + \omega^2 x_1 - \Omega_c^2 x_2 = E_0 e^{-i\omega st} \quad \ddot{x}_2 + \gamma_2 \dot{x}_2 + \omega^2 x_2 - \Omega_c^2 x_1 = 0$$

$$\text{Let } x_1 = N e^{-i\omega st} \text{ \& } x_2 = M e^{-i\omega st}$$

Solving the eq(3) for M , & then eq(4) for N we get,

$$M = \frac{\Omega_c^4 N}{(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s)} \quad N = \frac{(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s)}{(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_1 \omega_s)(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s) - \Omega_c^4}$$

Therefore the value of x_1 will be:

$$x_1 = \frac{E_0 e^{-i\omega st} (\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s)}{(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_1 \omega_s)(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s) - \Omega_c^4}$$

& therefore the power will be:

$$P = \frac{2\pi i E_0^2 \omega_s e^{-i\omega st} (\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s)}{(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_1 \omega_s)(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s) - \Omega_c^4}$$

When $\omega^2 = \omega_s^2$ the oscillating current flow balances the imposed Voltage V_s , therefore the power transfer gets maximum and then as $\omega^2 > \omega_s^2$ there is a Voltage Drop. The voltage drop can be used to analogically represent the Absorption Gap due to the Stark Splitting of energy state $|2\rangle$ we have seen earlier.

Fig (4): Coupled Oscillatory Response. Note the Voltage drop at about .016 sec.

Fig (5): Non-Coupled Oscillatory Response. No Voltage Drop.

If a graph of Absorption vs Frequency of an EIT System is plotted then we would find a similar curve as Fig (4).

A major application of the EIT System as mentioned earlier is to produce subluminal and superluminal light. Changing the Absorption Energy Gap between $|1\rangle$ and $|2\rangle$ lead to change in property of refractive index of the medium, so refractive index varies with respect to the “probe” and “pump” laser frequencies. The following analysis would prove thus and that the increase in refractive index lowers the group velocity of the “probe” laser beam.

We have derived earlier that the function of charge in an EIT system is

$$x_1 = \frac{E_0 e^{-i\omega t} (\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s)}{(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_1 \omega_s)(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s) - \Omega_c^4}$$

If an electric field E is applied on the charge $x1$, and there N_e number of free charges then the Polarization in the medium will be:

$$P = - \frac{EN_e E_0 e^{-i\omega st} (\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s)}{(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_1 \omega_s)(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s) - \Omega_c^4}$$

$$\chi E = - \frac{EN_e E_0 e^{-i\omega st} (\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s)}{(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_1 \omega_s)(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s) - \Omega_c^4}$$

where χ is electrical susceptibility of medium.

We also know that if ϵ is the electrical permittivity of the medium then,

$$\epsilon = \epsilon_0 + \chi$$

Substituting for χ in the equation we get,

$$\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_0} = 1 + \frac{N_e E_0 e^{-i\omega st} (\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s)}{(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_1 \omega_s)(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s) - \Omega_c^4}$$

We know that $\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_0}$ is square of η the refractive index of the medium,

$$\eta^2 = 1 + \frac{N_e E_0 e^{-i\omega st} (\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s)}{(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_1 \omega_s)(\omega^2 - \omega_s^2 - i\gamma_2 \omega_s) - \Omega_c^4}$$

So, we showed that refractive index of the medium depends on the pump frequency of laser ω_s and probe frequency of laser Ω_c , therefore when $\omega^2 = \omega_s^2$ the η is maximum.

We also know that group velocity of light depends on the group refractive index as $\eta_g = \frac{c}{v_g}$, so when the η_g attains maxima v_g attains minima. The slow light can also be used to store stopped light pulses in a medium and to retrieve it again, which are of great applications in quantum information storage.

Fig(5a) Slow Light Experiment (5b) Quantum Information Storage

Another application is to produce Logic Signalling Gate using two coupled photon generators, using an EIT System, which can be done by sending coupled signals which interfere & produce to an output of the gate much the same way a Binary Circuit does. Some such Quantum Gates are called Hadamard Gate, Arbitrary Rotation Gate etc, in which single input polarised laser beams are used.

Fig (5): Hadamard gate, Arbitrary Rotation gate and PBS gate

The quantum mechanical system of electromagnetically induced transparency has covered many miles since its inception in 1990; many practical applications & elaborate experiments have been done by many researchers worldwide, and it is currently one of the most active research areas in quantum optics. In this report we have proved thus the Laser Electromagnetic fields can change the materialistic macroscopic property of the whole system itself like energy absorption, refractive index, dispersion etc. which gives some serious clue about the nature of reality in the Quantum realm itself. Therefore, days are not far away when our understanding of the microscopic systems and their collective influence in producing the effects in the macroscopic world will go through dramatic change.